

STUDY OF DAMAGE MORPHOLOGY IN LAMINATES BY INHOMOGENEOUS PERCOLATION MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The problem of inhomogeneous percolation arose recently in our damage evolution modeling in laminates. The layered inhomogeneous distribution of the crack concentration in plies was obtained by stochastic analysis. In this paper, a percolation model is developed and applied to evaluate damage morphology in a laminate. Inhomogeneous probability distribution introduces anisotropy in the problem. Unlike the well-known anisotropic percolation models, where anisotropy results from the directional dependence of connectivity rules, geometry of the present model is anisotropic itself. Monte Carlo simulations of the percolation on a square lattice with anisotropic inhomogeneous probability distribution are reported. Finite size scaling is used for data analysis. As inhomogeneity increases the critical probability decreases whereas the correlation length exponent remains, within computational errors, the same as in classical 2D percolation. Cluster size, shape, and orientation factors are introduced and studied at different probability levels. Parameters of cluster distributions are calculated and compared to the results of a homogeneous model. Potential application of the results in interacting crack models are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The failure in composites is a complicated process of initiation, accumulation, and coalescence of damage of several modes. This process is governed by a number of random factors such as random material properties of constituents, random microstructure, and random loading. Damage concentration and morphology affect the stiffness and unstable failure characteristics of a composite. A discipline studying morphology and properties of random multicomponent systems is the percolation theory [1]. Results of percolation analysis show that an infinite cluster of microcracks emerges at the crack concentrations significantly lower than the maximum concentration. Some issues of fracture in disordered materials have been recently studied by percolation approach [2]. Simple illustrative computer models have been developed [3]. In this paper, an attempt is made to study progressive damage morphology in laminates by percolation model. A stochastic mesomechanics model developed in [4-6] provides mechanical background for this analysis. The model provides

an information on damage in composite laminae in terms of damage probability. Due to the laminar geometry under consideration, the percolation problem is inhomogeneous and anisotropic.

The problem of anisotropic percolation has been the subject of several investigations. In these studies, anisotropy was induced by the anisotropy of properties [7,8] or shapes [8-11] of inclusions or by the orientation dependence of connectivity rules [12,13]. In present paper, a new type of anisotropy in random systems is introduced and analyzed: the one due to a spatial inhomogeneity of probability of crack formation in plies. In general, there are several kinds of cracks in each ply interacting with each other. Probability of crack formation depends on the material properties and orientation of plies in a laminate and on the load applied. For lay-ups with alternate ply orientation (cross-ply or angle-ply laminates), a simple periodic probability distribution may be observed. As a first approximation we will assume that microcracks of different modes are similar for percolation analysis. A problem of cracks formation, accumulation and propagation through the thickness of laminate is then anisotropic site percolation in two dimensions with probability of crack formation in a ply equal to sum of probabilities of cracks of different kinds. In developing statistical models for damage in solids, clusters statistics are of primary importance, especially the size, shape, and orientation statistics [2]. However, in order to investigate clusters properties, it is necessary first to study the critical behavior of a system [14,15]. A brief report on percolation analysis of thresholds for layered probability distribution was published in [16]. The present paper generalizes and extends these results. First, the detailed threshold analysis is presented. Then, new results on cluster morphology in a layered inhomogeneous percolation system are reported.

MONTE-CARLO MODEL

The model analyzed is a simple square lattice of side b consisting of rows with alternating probabilities of occupancy of sites p_1 and p_2 . The average probability of occupancy on the lattice is $p = (p_1 + p_2)/2$. The inhomogeneity parameter is $c = p_1/p_2$. Due to the symmetry of problem we can arbitrarily choose $p_1 \leq p_2$, then $c \in [0, 1]$. Let us define p_h as a probability p at percolation in horizontal direction (along the rows), and p_v as a probability at percolation in vertical direction. It is clear that for $c \neq 1$ the system exhibits anisotropic percolation on finite lattices, but percolation thresholds p_h, p_v tend to isotropic limit $p_c(c)$ when lattice size increases.

THRESHOLD ANALYSIS

For any finite lattice percolation thresholds p_v, p_h are random and their distributions $L(c, b; p_v)$ and $L(c, b; p_h)$ are the narrower the larger is the lattice. These distributions are expected to be roughly Gaussian and, according to finite size scaling considerations [15,17], both means $\langle p \rangle$ and deviations $\sigma = \langle (p - \langle p \rangle)^2 \rangle^{1/2}$ of distributions at any given c scale for sufficiently large b as

$$|p_c - \langle p \rangle| \sim b^{-1/\nu} \quad \sigma \sim b^{-1/\nu} \quad (1)$$

Here ν is a correlation length exponent. At each c , calculating $L(c, b; p_v)$ and $L(c, b; p_h)$ for a number of lattice sizes b and plotting $\sigma(b)$ in double logarithmic coordinates, ν can be obtained from (1) as a slope of the curve. Then, interpolation of $\langle p \rangle(b^{-1/\nu})$ to $b^{-1/\nu} = 0$ gives an estimate for p_c . A numerical analysis is performed by the method analogous to [18]. A master set of random integers is formed in the computer memory; then a working set of zeros and unities is created according to given fixed c and trial value of p ; this set is analyzed for the existence of spanning cluster; concentration p is increased or decreased depending on the results of the search. Using this procedure

percolation thresholds in two directions p_h and p_v are obtained for the i -th realization with an accuracy defined by $\max[1/b^2, 1/\text{RAND_MAX}]$, where RAND_MAX is a maximum value returned by random generator. In our case $\text{RAND_MAX} = 32767$. After that another master set is examined and distributions $L(c, b; p_v)$, $L(c, b; p_h)$ are calculated. Economic computer code featuring dynamic memory allocation is written in C. Calculations are performed on CRAY-2 computer.

Unlike homogeneous percolation where the maximum probability p on a lattice is equal to 1 and percolation threshold can always be achieved by increasing p , in the case of inhomogeneous percolation maximum p is $(1+c)/2$. At this probability $p_2 = 1$ and $p_1 = c \leq 1$. Hence, for finite lattice there exists non-zero probability of absence of percolation path in vertical direction (across the rows) at maximal concentration. This probability is the higher the smaller is the lattice size and the higher is the inhomogeneity. Probability of existence of percolation path in v direction at maximum $p = (1+c)/2$ is given by

$$p_{v_c} = [1 - (1-c)^b]^{b/2} \tag{2}$$

Figure 1a shows the variation of p_{v_c} with lattice size for several values of c . Experimental points are obtained as a ratio of number of realizations in which percolation path existed at maximum concentration to total number of trials. Analysis of distributions $L(c, b; p_v)$ shows that when p_{v_c} is sufficiently lower than unity, the distributions become considerably non-Gaussian (one-sided). Minimal lattice size $b_{min}(c)$ to be employed in numerical analysis can be determined then from (2) as one for which $p_{v_c} \geq p_{v_{min}}$. Results of numerical solution of (2) for b (Figure 1b) show that b_{min} grows fast with inhomogeneity level $1/c$ and $p_{v_{min}}$ requested.

The program is checked on a homogeneous case $c = 1$. Following range of b is investigated 10, 20, 40, 80, 160, 320, 640. Obtained threshold distributions are checked for normality by calculating third and fourth moments. Comparisons with known values for Gaussians show that 0.95 confidence level is not violated. Calculated means and deviations of distributions $L(1, b; p_v)$ and $L(1, b; p_h)$ are given in Table 1. N represents number of realizations. Percolation thresholds in two directions for homogeneous case are fairly isotropic. Comparisons with numerical data [19] show good agreement. Distributions $L(c, b; p_v)$ and $L(c, b; p_h)$ are calculated for inhomogeneities $c = 0.8, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2, \text{ and } 0.1$. A minimal lattice size is selected using (2). An additional lattice size $b=1280$ is employed in the analysis. Check for normality does not reveal violation of the 0.95 confidence level. Calculated means and deviations of threshold distributions are listed in Table 1. Figure 2a shows the threshold deviations plotted as functions of b in double logarithmic coordinates.

FIGURE 1. (a) Variation of probability of existence of percolation in vertical direction at maximum concentration with lattice size; points - numerical experiment; numbers indicate inhomogeneity parameter c . (b) Variation of minimal lattice size with c for several probability levels $p_{v_{min}}$.

TABLE I. Means and deviations of threshold distributions at various inhomogeneity levels.

	b	N	$\langle p_w \rangle$	σ_w	$\langle p_h \rangle$	σ_h
c=1.0	10	20000	.5907	.0736	.5903	.0741
	20	10000	.5919	.0486	.5925	.0489
	40	4000	.5927	.0301	.5921	.0304
	80	2000	.5917	.0190	.5922	.0188
	160	703	.5934	.0108	.5932	.0115
	320	198	.5929	.0069	.5922	.0062
	640	203	.5928	.0046	.5920	.0039
c=0.8	10	8000	.5851	.0868	.5792	.0841
	20	4000	.5883	.0534	.5843	.0527
	40	2000	.5887	.0326	.5864	.0318
	80	1000	.5887	.0202	.5874	.0202
	160	681	.5888	.0122	.5883	.0118
	320	184	.5883	.0069	.5883	.0062
	640	48	.5889	.0038	.5888	.0033
	1280	12	.5894	.0017	.5879	.0021
c=0.6	10	8000	.5811	.0817	.5551	.0769
	20	4000	.5803	.0498	.5637	.0479
	40	2000	.5794	.0295	.5686	.0298
	80	1000	.5777	.0180	.5716	.0183
	160	770	.5767	.0106	.5731	.0103
	320	208	.5756	.0066	.5737	.0062
	640	56	.5742	.0035	.5734	.0032
	1280	12	.5762	.0023	.5756	.0024
c=0.4	20	4000	.5684	.0435	.5266	.0423
	40	2000	.5632	.0262	.5370	.0255
	80	1000	.5581	.0154	.5426	.0149
	160	759	.5551	.0089	.5457	.0089
	320	199	.5532	.0053	.5472	.00581
	640	51	.5526	.0035	.5490	.0029
	1280	12	.5512	.0014	.5501	.0015
c=0.2	40	2000	.5447	.0198	.4964	.0209
	80	1000	.5348	.0124	.5059	.0128
	160	891	.5294	.0078	.5115	.0074
	320	241	.5255	.0044	.5150	.0044
	640	69	.5229	.0027	.5170	.0028
	1280	17	.5225	.0009	.5191	.0014
c=0.1	80	1000	.5274	.0092	.4875	.0107
	160	911	.5190	.0060	.4947	.0063
	320	248	.5145	.0035	.4999	.0041
	640	68	.5107	.0019	.5022	.0021
	1280	16	.5092	.0013	.5041	.0014

FIGURE 2. (a) Double logarithmic plots $\sigma(b)$ and their linear least square fits; gray - σ_h , black - σ_v ; $c=0.1,0.2,0.4,0.6$, and 0.8 . (b) Plots $\langle p \rangle(b^{-1/\nu})$ and their linear least square fits for various c ; gray - p_h , black - p_v [16].

The error bars for σ are calculated by

$$\Delta\sigma = \frac{1}{2\sigma\sqrt{N}} \sqrt{\langle (p_i - \langle p \rangle)^4 \rangle - \langle (p_i - \langle p \rangle)^2 \rangle^2} \quad (3)$$

Correlation length exponents, obtained by evaluating the slope of the linear least square fits at higher b , are given in Table 2. Within an experimental error, they coincide with classical value $\nu = 4/3$ for two dimensions which is consistent with the concept of universality confirmed for other anisotropic systems in [7,10,13]. Figure 2b shows dependences of $\langle p \rangle$ on $b^{-1/\nu}$. Error bars for threshold means, estimated as $\Delta\langle p \rangle = \sigma/\sqrt{N}$, do not exceed data point size on Figure 2b. Lines represent linear least square fit for larger lattices. It is seen that linear approximations for thresholds in vertical and horizontal directions tend to a single limit at each value of c examined. Their intersection with the ordinate axis gives the “true” value of p_c for a given c . Summary of estimates of $p_c(c)$ is shown in Table 2. It is seen that as inhomogeneity increases, percolation threshold decreases. The limit for p_c when $c \rightarrow 0$ is 0.5 . Note that experimentally obtained dependence $p_c(c)$ is not a linear variation between the limits $p_0 = 0.5$ and $p_1 = 0.5927$ [16].

TABLE 2. Summary on correlation length exponents and percolation thresholds at various inhomogeneity levels [16].

c	ν_v	ν_h	p_c
1	1.45	1.36	.5927
0.8	1.24	1.26	.5888
0.6	1.33	1.34	.5750
0.4	1.27	1.26	.5506
0.2	1.38	1.36	.5206
0.1	1.36	1.31	.5064

CLUSTER SIZE, SHAPE, AND ORIENTATION FACTORS

A developed inhomogeneous percolation model was used for Monte-Carlo analysis of cluster size, shape, and orientation distributions at different average concentrations and inhomogeneities. Results of numerical analysis for $b=50$ and $c=0.1$ are presented in Figures 3-5. In these figures, a dashed vertical line indicates critical concentration for an infinite system. Figure 3 shows

variations of a mean cluster length and cluster length deviation with an average crack concentration p . The cluster length in horizontal and vertical directions is defined as a difference between the maximal and minimal site coordinates in corresponding directions. It is measured in units of a length of a characteristic crack representing the site in the numerical model. Figure 4 shows variations of maximal and mean aspect ratios of clusters. The aspect ratio is defined as a ratio of the maximal and minimal cluster extensions. Maximal aspect ratios of clusters oriented in horizontal and vertical directions are shown separately in Figure 4a. An average cluster orientation (Figure 5a) is evaluated as a difference in volume fractions of clusters extended in horizontal and vertical directions. A mean weighted orientation, with a weight equal to cluster aspect ratio, is presented in Figure 5b. Results of analogous calculations for the classical homogeneous percolation ($c=1$) are shown in Figures 6-8. Comparisons of Figures 3,4 and 6,7 show that clusters are significantly more anisodiametric in case of inhomogeneous percolation. This "stretching" is especially remarkable at

FIGURE 3. Variation of (a) mean and (b) standard deviation of cluster length distributions with average damage concentration at $c=0.1$. Gray - horizontal, black - vertical direction.

FIGURE 4. Variation of (a) maximal and (b) mean cluster aspect ratio with average damage concentration at $c=0.1$. In (a), gray - horizontal, black - vertical direction.

FIGURE 5. Variation of (a) mean and (b) weighted mean cluster orientation parameter with average damage concentration at $c=0.1$.

FIGURE 6. Variation of (a) mean and (b) standard deviation of cluster length distribution with average damage concentration at $c=1$. Gray - horizontal, black - vertical direction.

FIGURE 7. Variation of (a) maximum and (b) mean cluster aspect ratio with average damage concentration at $c=1$. In (a), gray - horizontal, black - vertical direction.

FIGURE 8. Variation of (a) mean and (b) weighted mean cluster orientation parameter with average damage concentration at $c=1$.

concentrations close to critical (see Figure 4). While there is no preferred orientation of clusters in case of homogeneous percolation (Figure 8), for layered inhomogeneous probability distribution, the orientation grows steadily with average concentration up to critical concentration (Figure 5).

CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of damage morphology in laminates with an alternate lay-up is performed by means of a two-dimensional inhomogeneous percolation model. Results on percolation threshold can be applied to specify final failure criterion. Results on cluster size, shape, and orientation can be used in models of crack interaction, such as models [20-23]. This can provide an effective feedback to the stochastic damage evolution model [4-6].

REFERENCES

1. Percolation Structures and Processes, G. Deutscher, R. Zallen, and J. Adler, Eds., *Annales of the Israel Physical Society*, Vol. 5, The Israel Physical Society, Jerusalem, 1983.
2. Statistical Models for the Fracture of Disordered Media, H.J. Herrmann and S. Roux, Eds., Elsevier, New York, 1990.
3. Broberg, K.B., "Computer Demonstration of Crack Growth," *International Journal of Fracture*, Vol. 42, 1990, pp. 277-285.
4. Dzenis, Y.A., Joshi, S.P., and Bogdanovich, A.E., "Damage Evolution Modeling in Orthotropic Laminated Composites", *AIAA Journal*, 1994, Vol. 32, No 2, pp. 357-364.
5. Dzenis, Y.A., Joshi, S.P., and Bogdanovich, A.E., "Behavior of Laminated Composites Under Monotonically Increasing Random Load", *AIAA Journal*, 1993, Vol. 31, No 12, pp. 2329-2334.
6. Dzenis, Y.A., "Stochastic Damage Evolution Modeling in Laminates", *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 1995, in press.
7. Lobb, C.J., Frank, D.J., and Tinkham, M., "Percolative Conduction in Anisotropic Media: A Renormalization Approach," *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol. 23, 1981, pp. 2262-2268.
8. Shklovskii, B.I., "Anisotropy of Percolation Conduction," *Phys. Stat. Sol.*, Vol. 85, 1978, pp. K111-K114.
9. Carmona, F., Barreau, F., Delhaes, P., and Canet, R., "An Experimental Model for Studying the Effect of Anisotropy on Percolative Conduction," *J. Physique-Letters* Vol. 41, 1980, pp. L531-L534.
10. Boissonade, J., Barreau, F., and Carmona, F., "The Percolation of Fibers with Random Orientations: a Monte Carlo Study," *J. Phys. A: Math. Gen.*, Vol. 16, 1983, pp. 2777-2787.
11. Smith, L.N. and Lobb, C.J., "Percolation in Two-Dimensional Conductor-Insulator Networks with Controllable Anisotropy," *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol. 20, 1979, pp. 3653-3658.
12. Blanc, R., Mitescu, C. D., and Thrennot, G., "Percolation Anisotrope: Conductivite d'un Reseau Carre de Liens Aleatoires," *J. Physique*, Vol. 41, 1980, pp. 387- 391.
13. Redner, S. and Stanley, H.E., "Anisotropic Bond Percolation," *J. Phys. A: Math. Gen.*, Vol. 12, 1979, pp. 12671283.
14. Kertesz, J., Stauffer, D., and Coniglio, A., "Clusters for Random and Interacting Percolation," *Percolation Structures and Processes*, G. Deutscher, R. Zallen, and J. Adler, Eds., The Israel Physical Society, 1983, pp. 121-147.
15. Levinshstein, M.E., Shklovskii, B.I., Shur, M.S., and Efros, A.L., "The Relation Between the Critical Exponents of Percolation Theory," *Sov. Phys.-JETP*, Vol. 42, 1976, pp. 197-200.
16. Dzenis, Y.A. and Joshi, S.P., "Inhomogeneous Anisotropic Percolation: Two-Dimensional Numerical Threshold Analysis," *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol. 49, 1994, pp. 3566-3568.
17. Rousseny, J., et al., "Size Dependence of the Percolation Threshold of Square and Triangular Networks," *Physique-Letters*, Vol. 37, 1976, pp. L99-L101.
18. Skal, A.S. and Shklovskii, B.I., "Topology of the Infinite Cluster in the Theory of Percolation and Doped Conductivity," *Sov. Phys. Semicond.*, Vol. 8, 1975, pp. 1029-1592.
19. Reynolds, P.J., Stanley, H.E., and Klein, W. "Large-Cell Monte Carlo Renormalization Group for Percolation," *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol. 21, 1980, pp. 1223-1245.
20. Ju, J.W., "On Two-Dimensional Micromechanical Damage Models for Brittle Solids with Interacting Microcracks," *Mechanics of Failure of Quasi-Brittle Materials*, S.P. Shah, S.E. Swartz, and M.L. Wang, Eds., Elsevier, New York, 1990, pp. 105-114.
21. Chudnovsky, A. and Wu, S., "Effect of Crack-Microcrack Interaction on energy Release Rates," *International Journal of Fracture*, Vol. 44, 1990, pp. 43-56.
22. Mauge, C. and Kachanov, M., "Anisotropic Material with Interacting Arbitrarily Oriented Cracks. Stress Intensity Factors and Crack-Microcrack Interactions," *International Journal of Fracture*, Vol. 65, 1994, pp. 115-139.
23. Lua, Y.J., Liu, W.K., and Belytschko, T., "A Stochastic Damage Model for the Rupture Prediction of a Multi-Phase Solid. Part I: Parametric Studies," *International Journal of Fracture*, Vol. 55, 1992, pp. 321-340.